

INVESTIGATION OF THE DE-ASPALTING PROCESS OF GOUDRON UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF A PRE-MAGNETIC FIELD**Khalafova Irada A.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Technical Sciences, Assistant professor
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AZ 1010, Baku city, Azadliq avenue, 20***Abstract**

The catalytic cracking of vacuum gas oil, as well as its mixture with tar deasphalted oil, the decaying molecules of which form correlated ions in the singlet state, has been studied. Under the influence of a magnetic field, a transition of ions from a singlet state to one of the triplet states is observed. The probability of recombination of diffusive ions and radicals, according to literature data, increases with increasing magnetic field induction.

Keywords: asphalt removal, magnetic field, goudron, catalytic cracking, expansion rate, temperature, solvents

Introduction

In order to expand oil refining, many laboratories are now conducting extensive research to develop technology to improve the efficiency of motor fuels by incorporating heavy oil residues (HOR) into the process. As you know, these residues contain large amounts of resins, asphaltenes, sulfur-containing compounds and contain almost all of the metals in oil. Asphaltenes and resins are high molecular weight components of HOR and cause complex technological problems during catalytic processing of residues. They therefore need to be pre-enriched (improved in composition) to form heavy oil residues.

This is done in two ways: removal of carbon and addition of hydrogen. Other purification processes are also available, such as solvent extraction of asphaltenes and resins. The choice of the best option depends on many factors: the characteristics of the available oil, market conditions, the structure of the Oil Refinery and the distribution of products to the facilities. Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the following methods are used to increase the sources of raw materials for catalytic cracking: Water cleaning of HOR, cleaning of asphalt of HOR, direct catalytic cracking of HOR, development of new catalytic systems, including modification of raw materials with various activating additives.

Today, the main process that enables deeper processing of petroleum products is catalytic cracking. The main objective is to increase the yield of the desired (final) product and reduce coke deposition on the catalyst [1-3]. This problem is solved in different ways:

1) In catalytic cracking, raw materials are activated with various surfactants, e.g. natural and synthetic naphthenic acids, distilled bitumen, selective oil extract, heavy catalytic cracking gas oil, etc.

2) Passivation of compounds such as heavy metals, stibium, tin, phosphorus, etc. that poison the catalyst.

3) Developing more efficient new catalytic systems.

4) Modernization of the catalytic cracking reactor-regenerator unit.

From this point of view, the study of the degradation of the vacuum gasoil mixture obtained from Baku oils with non-asphalted resin is a topical problem in the modern oil refining industry [4-7].

The main purpose of the work:

1) Investigation of goudron de-asphalting with various hydrocarbon solvents, investigation of goudron's magnetic de-asphalting process.

2) Determination of the optimum ratio and optimum conditions for the cracking of unasphalted goudron and vacuum gasoil mixtures in industrial catalysts.

3) Study of catalytic cracking of Baku oils vacuum gasoil and its mixture with deasphalted goudron in a magnetic field.

4) Determination of the effect of goudron deasphalting and magnetic field on the quality of catalytic cracking products.

Magnetic exposure of the goudron in the de-asphalting process was first applied in this period. The amount of asphaltene and resin in the product purified from asphalt has been shown to decrease during the magnetic treatment of goudron. The optimal ratio of vacuum gas oil mixed with tar extracted from asphalt during catalytic cracking was determined. A magnetic

field was applied for the first time in the catalytic cracking process and the optimum strength of the magnetic field was determined. It has been shown that during magnetic field fractionation of the feedstock mixture, catalytic cracking indicators improve, gasoline yield increases, coke formation decreases and the quality of the products obtained improves.

Experimental part

The aim is to broaden the feedstock base for the catalytic cracking of heavy oil residues. This work was carried out without any modifications to industrial catalysts. The positive effect of magnetic field on deasphalting and catalytic cracking processes was determined. The study of the catalytic cracking of a mixture of vacuum gasoil and de-asphalted tar in a magnetic field could be the basis for the production of high-octane gasoline [7-10].

As seen in the literature, it is possible to intensify the de-asphalting process with mechanical waves,

especially ultrasonic waves. From this point of view, it is interesting to check the influence of the pre-treatment of raw materials on the asphaltting process. Experiments were carried out at different solvent ratios: feedstock, temperature and magnetic induction flux. Asphalt was removed and its properties were studied [11-14].

To determine the optimum magnetic induction flux strength, experiments were performed at different values of the magnetic field at 160 °C at different solvent:raw material ratios of 4 : 1. Photo 1 shows the changes in the amount of resin and asphaltene in gasoline and pentane defaults. As can be seen from this curve, the amount of resin and asphaltene in both deasphalting agents decreases with increasing magnetic field from 0.2 Tl to 1.4 Tl. 1.4Tl is optimal because at this time the amount of asphaltene and resin is minimal (figure 1) [1].

Figure 1. Dependence of asphaltene and resin content in the deasphalting process on magnetic field

In order to further investigate the effect of magnetic field on the deasphalting process, several experiments were carried out with different solvent:feedstock ratios, at 160 °C temperature and 1.4 Tl magnetic field [5-8]. The results of these experiments are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Physico-chemical properties of the deasphalting agents obtained during the magnetic effect treatment of tar at different solvent : feedstock ratios at 160 °C temperature

The pointers	Yield, mass fraction, %	Density, g/cm ³	Sulfur, mass fraction, %	Viscosity at 100 °C, mm ² /s	Coking, %	Content, %:		
						Tar	Asphaltene	
Pentane	2 : 1	64	0,8899	1,19	111	6,3	4,3	0,8
	3 : 1	60	0,8850	1,09	107	6,1	3,8	0,6
	4 : 1	55	0,8835	1,04	104	6,0	3,0	0,26
	5 : 1	53	0,8825	1,02	102	5,9	2,8	0,25
Hexane	2 : 1	70	0,8960	1,18	112	6,6	4,6	1,2
	3 : 1	67	0,8930	1,10	110	6,4	4,1	0,7
	4 : 1	59	0,8900	1,07	107	6,3	3,2	0,3
	5 : 1	55	0,8995	1,06	106	6,2	3,1	0,28
Gasoline	2 : 1	77	0,9100	2,0	118	7,3	8,3	1,5
	3 : 1	70	0,9030	1,4	112	6,7	6,5	0,8
	4 : 1	63	0,8915	1,12	110	6,4	4,0	0,32
	5 : 1	60	0,8900	1,05	108	6,3	3,7	0,31

Table 1 shows the physico-chemical properties of the de-asphalting agents obtained with different solvent:feedstock ratios at 160 °C and 1.4 Tl magnetic field. Thus, the performance of the deasphalting process is greatly improved when goudron is pretreated with a magnetic field. In pentane deasphalting at a 4 : 1 ratio, the mass fraction of resin decreases from 3.2 % to 3.0 %, the amount of asphaltene decreases from 0.3 % to 0.26 % and the degree of coking decreases from 6.4 % to 6 % [15-18].

The viscosity decreases slightly from 105 to 104 mm²/cm², also the mass fraction of sulphur changes slightly from 1.06 % to 1.04 % and the density decreases, while the deasphalting efficiency decreases by 4 %. The quality difference of deasphalting increases as the molecular weight of the solvent increases, so that when the solvent is heptane, the content of asphaltenes and resins decreases to 3.4 % - 3.2 % and 0.35 % - 0.3 % respectively [16-18]. The coking rate drops to 6.8 % - 6.3 %. Viscosity, sulfur content and density change as in pentane deasphalting. Asphalt removal efficiency decreases by 68 % - 59 %, i.e. by 9 %. When the solvent is gasoline, the mass fraction of asphaltenes decreases from 0.4 % to 0.32 %, the mass fraction of resins to 4.6-4.0 %, coking to 6.9-6.4 %, the remaining amounts vary as in the case of hexane solvent. Therefore, both with and without magnetic treatment, the optimal solvent:feedstock ratio can be considered to be 4 : 1.

Conclusions

As a result of the research, it was shown that it is possible to create a combined unit for de-asphalting goudron and catalytic cracking. It is planned to use industrial zeolite catalyst in this unit. It is proposed to use a mixture of asphalt-free goudron and vacuum gas oil in a ratio of 13 : 87 % by volume as feedstock for the catalytic cracking unit.

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